

Project Brief

The case study to be introduced is a part of a larger study on developing a design methodology for Mass Personalization (MP). MP is a paradigm that aims to tailor the products to meet individual needs of customers, with near mass production efficiency. Therefore, instead of the configuration process in mass customization; in MP, the product undergoes fundamental changes, and it is co-created with the customer on a higher level of individualization. The design methodology proposed for MP covers how to develop products open to customer modification, and how to automate customer co-creation process. Therefore, the presented study on knitted footwear illustrates the application of this methodology.

Personalization in footwear is nothing new; it has been practiced by shoemakers producing bespoke shoes. Inherently, the cost of an artisanal product is higher than a mass-produced counterpart. However, customer willingness to pay for a personalized shoe is only 10 to 30% more than a mass-produced one. A major reason of interest in personalization is the customers' need of proper fit and comfort. Standardized footwear with mass production results in a poor fit, which is found to cause several foot-related problems. Another motivation personalization is that footwear is also a fashion product and provides an opportunity of self-expression to customers. Therefore, the uniqueness and mass efficiency offered by MP is very suitable for footwear.

In this study, personalized footwear design case with a knitted upper, and a 3D printed sole is exemplified. Digital knitting and 3D printing are used for this study as promising technologies for footwear. The reason of choosing these two technologies is that they both provide design personalization opportunities, the flexibility needed for design automation and mass efficiency. The given example is the development of a two-component shoe, only the upper and sole are considered (Fig. 1).

The shoe is personalized in terms of fit, comfort, and appearance in this scenario (Fig. 1). In terms of fit, nearest fit to a standard size principle is used. The standard sizing and grading measures are changed with quarter increments to match the customer feet measurements. The comfort and appearance of the shoe is adapted through modifying the knitting properties of the shoe upper. The parameters changed are yarn material, color, count and knit pattern. Based on the changing parameters, we form a solution space, where all the possible design options are present. We also form a design space for the user, where user can specify a range of requirements on the shoe. Ultimately, a shoe template is created, we call it as a seed design, which allows the user to personalize a pair with certain decisions.

We first examine the relationship between the user's personalization requirements and the design parameters of the shoe (Fig. 2). Based on this examination, a design solution algorithm is devised to get user requirements as input and set the design parameters as output. The purpose of the algorithm is both to automate the personalization process of the shoe, and to ensure a realizable final design. In this scenario, the user interacts with an online product configurator to co-create a personalized pair with the design solution algorithm behind. It is an interactive process, which means with every user decision, the algorithm updates the design and informs the user about further possible design options.

Figure 1. Knitted footwear personalization scenario (left), a prototype produced based on the scenario (right).

Personalised fit	Waist girth		X				
	Instep girth		X				
	Short heel girth		X				
	Length	X					
Graphical pattern	Flexibility			X			X
	Weight					X	X
	Permeability			X		X	X
	Heat resistance			X		X	X
Graphical pattern	Color				X		
	Layout	C	C				
	Knit pattern						X
		Last sizing	Last grading	Yarn material	Yarn color	Yarn count	Knit pattern

Figure 2. Dependency matrix of personalization requirements and design parameters. X denotes for a dependency, and C denotes for a constraint.

Open questions to evaluate the case study

At the end of the presentation of the study, you will be asked to evaluate the study based on 5 perspectives. For each perspective, you will be asked to comment on possible benefits or limitations, and suggestions, if any.

	Benefits	Limitations	Remarks
Applicability			
Feasibility (technical)			
Potential (business)			
User experience / satisfaction			
In comparison to existing applications			